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- Study on Agricultural University Libraries of North East India
- Research Contribution and Collaboration Pattern
- Contribution of Jadavpur University in Science & Technology
- Usage Of N-LIST E-Resources
- Innovative Services in University Libraries

Indian Association of Special Libraries & Information Centres

Kolkata - 700054

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A Peer-Reviewed Quarterly Journal

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Editorial Office : IASLIC, P-291, CIT Scheme No 6M, Kankurgachi, Kolkata 700054, WB, India

✉ iaslic.journal@gmail.com ☎ +91 33 2362 9651

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All correspondences relating to the Journal should be addressed to :

The Editor, IASLIC Bulletin, P 291, CIT Scheme No. 6M, Kankurgachi, Kolkata - 700 054, WB, India

✉ iaslic.journal@gmail.com ☎ +91 33 2362 9651 📞 +91 9434243522

Agricultural University Libraries of North East India: An Empirical Study

Nabin Chandra Dey^a
Sanjay Kumar Singh^b

Abstract

Purpose: Agriculture is a source of livelihood to the majority of rural population in North East India. This paper traces the history of agricultural education and research in North East India since British period. Assam Agricultural University with nine constituent colleges and Central Agricultural University with ten constituent colleges are currently functional in the north eastern region imparting under graduate, post graduate and doctoral programs in various disciplines of Agricultural Sciences. The purpose of this study is to evaluate the constituent college libraries of these two agricultural universities of the North East India.

Methodology: Survey method has been adopted for this study. A structured questionnaire was administered among librarians of constituent colleges of Central Agricultural University and Assam Agricultural University.

Findings: The study found that the library expenditures of both the universities are in a decreasing trend. The libraries are partially automated and both the universities are suffering from low Internet bandwidth issues.

Originality: The study is an original research work mainly dealing with primary data collected through a survey in the constituent colleges of Central Agricultural University and Assam Agricultural University.

Keywords: Assam Agricultural University, Central Agricultural University, Hill Agriculture, Indian Council of Agricultural Research, Marginal Farmers, National Agricultural Research System, National Knowledge Network, Rainfed Agriculture.

Research Contribution and Collaboration Pattern of Assam University and Tezpur University: A Comparative Bibliometric Study

A K Sharma^a
Kumar Gaurav^b

Abstract

Purpose: Scientometric and bibliometric tools are helpful in measurement of scientific and research output activities of any organization through statistics. The impact of the output produced by any academic institutions in different fields varies extensively. In this article, a comparison of two central universities has been made to measure their productivity in terms of their publications as both the universities were established during the same year in North-Eastern Region.

Methodology: The data about the productivity of two Universities i.e. Assam University and Tezpur University have been downloaded from Web of Science (WoS) for twenty years (1997-2016) to compare the publication output and yearwise growth in terms of publications. For analysis of data MS-Excel is used for plotting the graphs and calculation.

Findings: There is a noticeable difference between the Universities in terms of productivity- qualitatively and quantitatively and national ranking by different agencies including National Assessment and Accreditation Council (NAAC) and National Institute of Ranking Framework (NIRF). The parameters set by NAAC gave 'A' Grading to Tezpur University and 'B' grade to Assam University. Also, the NIRF ranking of the Universities, Tezpur University was ranked 5th and Assam University 77th. The publication of Tezpur University were more in terms of quality and quantity.

Originality: In the present study, the productivity has been measured on the basis of research contribution of both Universities using Web of Science (WoS) data. The study is an original work of the authors.

Keywords: Citation Analysis, Assam University, Tezpur University, Bibliometric Study

Contribution of Jadavpur University in S&T as reflected in WoS Database during 2006-2015

Dhiman Mondal^a
Nitai Raychoudhury^b

Abstract

Purpose: The main purpose of this study is to assess the performance, trend and citation impact of research publications of faculty members of Jadavpur University.

Design/Methodology/Approach: The present scientometric study analyses the research publications of faculty members and researchers of Jadavpur University in last 10 years from 2006 to 2015 as reflected in Web of Science (WoS) database.

Findings: The study has identified 6895 articles including 1452 internationally collaborated articles with an increasing growth rate during the study period. The Polyhedron journal has been found as the most preferred journal. Maximum research articles have been published in Chemistry and allied disciplines. The citation analysis has indicated that the research articles especially with international collaboration have received good citations. The study recommended that the faculty members and researchers should select journals with high impact factor for disseminating research results. The researchers should go for more foreign collaboration for larger readership and international recognition.

Originality/Value: The trend and pattern of research output would throw some light to the administrators, planners, policy makers and funding agencies to take decision in fund allocation and in developing research infrastructure.

Keywords: Publication Productivity, Scientometric Study, Research Performance, Jadavpur University.

Usage Of N-LIST E-Resources in Select Degree Colleges affiliated to Panjab University, Chandigarh : A Critical Analysis

**Shivani Kaushal^a
Rupak Chakravarty^b**

Abstract

Purpose: This research paper aims at reflecting the usage pattern and the satisfaction level of the N-LIST consortium e-resources available in respective disciplines, about important databases, e-books and e-journals, recurring usage of information and knowledge.

Methodology/ Approach: A survey method have been used to analyse the usage of the N-LIST E-resources among the student and faculty members of the various select degree colleges affiliated to Panjab University, Chandigarh. A questionnaire method have been implied as a tool for collection of data from 32 select degree colleges in Punjab and Chandigarh. The total data was collected from the 466 out of 513 respondents. The total response rate is 90.84%. Out of 466 respondents, total 286 are users (faculty members and students) respondents and 180 are non-users (faculty members and students) respondents.

Findings: It is inferred that Mylibrary E-books and MathScinet are found to be the most useful amongst the faculty members and students respondents. Whereas 90.28% of faculty members respondents opined for Royal Society of Chemisty (RSC) as useful for their academic pursuits. On the contrary, 98.59% of student respondents considered 'Economic and Political Weekly' as useful for searching the N-LIST E-Journals. It can be inferred that there is non-significant difference in the usage of the N-LIST E-resources amongst the faculty members and students respondents.

Originality / Value: This study helps in identifying the strengths and weakness is of the consortium in evaluating the performance of N-LIST e-resources. The measures needed to be undertaken to make the N-LIST Consortium more effective and successful are also mentioned.

Keywords: E-Books, E-Journals, Bibliographical Databases, N-LIST, INFLIBNET, Panjab University, Statistical Analysis, Consortia

Proposing Innovative Services in University Libraries of North East India: A Case Study on Mizoram University Library System

B Lalhlimpuii^a

Abstract

Purpose : *The purposes of the study are to develop the resource collection in Mizoram University Central Library and to explore the possibilities of introducing some innovative information services towards maximum usage of resources provided by the Library.*

Methodology: *The interview method was adopted for the study. Questionnaire tool was used to collect the sample. Structured questionnaire was prepared for the library professionals to find out the information relating to the study and another structured questionnaire was developed for the users.*

Findings: *It is interesting to note that Mizoram University being a newly established university could develop a good collection of library resources within a very short span of time and has taken up digitization of Theses/Dissertations and other library resources such as rare book, out of print books, journals (bound volumes). Question papers could also be digitized. Users are more interested to access the materials at their homes instead of accessing them at the library. Users are unaware about many library resources which can be helpful for their academic requirements. Innovative services should be introduced to aware users.*

Originality/Value : *This study assesses the library services provided by Mizoram University Central Library and also measures the satisfaction of users with library services on definite parameters. This finding will help the Central Library of Mizoram University to improve their services and to introduce innovative services.*

Keywords : *Innovation, Library Services, Collection Development, Mizoram University, University Library, North East India*